

13th Irish Variety in Chemistry Education meeting

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Event Sponsors

Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, the Virtual Labs HCI P3 Initiative and the RSC Chemistry Education Research Group.

Summary

The Irish Variety in Chemistry Education meeting is held every two to three years and aims to share effective practice in chemistry teaching and related education research in higher education in Ireland and beyond. [The 13th meeting was held in Maynooth University on April 10th 2026.](#) This year, the meeting was followed by an event to celebrate the RSC Team Prize for Excellence in Higher Education being awarded to the Virtual Labs Team.

About the Irish Variety in Chemistry Education meeting

The meeting was founded by some members of the RSC Ireland Region Education Division including Dr Bill Byers and Dr Peter Childs. The 5th meeting in 2005 was the first to be held in Dublin Institute of Technology (now TU Dublin) in 2005. The next 7 meetings took place in DIT Kevin Street and the 12th Irish Variety in Chemistry meeting was held in 2024 on TU Dublin's Grangegorman campus for the first time and was co-organised with Maynooth University. This year is another first as the 13th was hosted by Maynooth University for the first time.

Attendees

40 people attended from 11 higher education institutions across the island of Ireland and we had one participant who travelled from the University of Manchester. Almost half of the participants had not attended the conference previously. One of the 5 lightning talks presenters was a chemistry education postgraduate student.

Target audience: academics and anyone else interested in chemistry teaching practice and research in higher education.

Programme

The programme (Tables 1 and 2) included contributions from two invited speakers, [Dr Giorgio Chianello](#), Queen Mary University of London and [Dr Kevin Morgan](#), Queen's University Belfast.

- Giorgio shared insights on how generative AI tools can be used to support chemistry education, learning and research. Within his presentation, he discussed both the potential and pitfalls of this technology, including the need to preserve the development of critical thinking (Figure 1).

Table 1. Schedule for morning session

Time	Speaker	Topic
10:15 - 10:30	Registration and refreshments	Location: Renehan Hall
10:30 - 10:40	Diego Montagner (MU HOD)	Welcome
<i>Chair</i>	Denise Rooney & Carmel Breslin (MU)	Session 1
10:40 - 10:55	Oral presentation - Joseph Byrne , School of Chemistry, University College Dublin	Implementing Universal Design for Learning in Chemistry Lecture Notes
10:55 - 11:10	Oral presentation - John O'Donoghue , School of Chemistry, Trinity College Dublin	From Optional to Core: Preparing for the arrival of the new Leaving Cert Chemistry Students in Sept 2027
11:10 - 11:15	Lightning talk 1 - Quancheng Hunter Hu , School of Chemistry, University College Dublin	Implementing Prequestioning in Irish Undergraduate Chemistry: Early Insights from a Diagnostic Feedback Intervention
11:15-11:20	Lightning talk 2 - Nicholas Mullins , Technological University of the Shannon- Midlands	Beyond TLC: Reimagining Classic Undergraduate Chemistry Experiments with Benchtop NMR
11:20-11:25		Opportunity for questions on the previous 2 lightning talks
11:25 - 11:35		Comfort Break
<i>Chair</i>	Frances Heaney (MU)	Keynote Session
11:35-12:35	Keynote Speaker: Giorgio Chianello , School of Physical & Chemical Sciences, Queen Mary University of London	Generative AI tools to support education, learning and research.
12:35-13:35		Lunch and opportunities for discussion

- Kevin is the 2025 winner of the Royal Society of Chemistry Excellence in Higher Education Prize. He shared his expertise on strategic leadership in chemistry education and gave examples of how he has created value, reach and impact across the educational spectrum. These included the 'Towards Greener Fragrances' schools project, [application of universal design to STEM higher education](#) and a [redesign of practical classes](#) (Figure 2).

The programme included five lightning talks on topics such as use of a benchtop NMR, pre-lecture questioning, short form videos for chemistry education, streamlining of chemical risk assessments and the Senpai Learn chemistry education team. The programme also included three oral presentations. These dealt with implementing universal design in chemistry, what to expect now the new chemistry Leaving Cert curriculum is running and the use of a medicinal herb garden to contextualise chemistry learning.

There were valuable opportunities to share ideas and experiences during coffee and lunch breaks (Figure 3).

Table 2. Schedule for afternoon session

Time	Speaker	Topic
<i>Chair</i>	Joseph Byrne (UCD)	Session 2
13:40-14:10	Speaker: Kevin Morgan , School of Chemistry & Chemical Engineering, Queen's University Belfast	Strategic Leadership in Chemistry Education: Creating Value, Reach and Impact Across the Educational Pipeline
14:10 - 14:25	Oral presentation - Claire McDonnell & Sarah Rawe , School of Chemical & BioPharmaceutical Sciences, Technological University Dublin	From small seeds towards... a living lab
14:25 - 14:30	Lightning talk 3 - Fun Man Fung , School of Chemistry, University College Dublin	Bringing Senpai Learn from Singapore to Ireland: Chemistry Education's Journey Across Continents
14:30-14:35	Lightning talk 4 - Justina Ugwah , School of Chemistry, University College Cork	From Lab Bench to Reels: Designing Short-Form Videos for Chemistry Education
14:35 - 14:40	Lightning talk 5 - Carl Poree , Department of Chemistry, University of Manchester	Less is more - good practice in CRA engagement with a low barrier to entry?
14:40 - 14:45		Opportunity for questions on the previous 3 lightning talks
14:45 - 15:00	Claire McDonnell & Sarah Rawe (TU Dublin)	Summing up, planning for the next Irish Variety Meeting and Closing

Figure 1. Dr Giorgio Chianello, invited speaker, examined the potential and pitfalls of gen AI technology. Other presentations included topics such as designing short form videos, incorporation of a benchtop NMR into teaching labs and use of a medicinal herb garden to contextualise chemistry

Figure 2. Dr Kevin Morgan, recipient of the 2025 RSC Excellence in Higher Education Prize, was an invited speaker

Figure 3. Coffee breaks and lunch were great opportunities to catch up with colleagues and meet participants who were new to Irish Variety in Chemistry Education

The meeting was followed by a celebration event for the [RSC Team Prize for Excellence in Higher Education](#) being awarded to the Virtual Labs Team (Figure 4). The Virtual Labs Team is made up of Maynooth University (Project Lead), University College Cork, Technological University of the Shannon, Dublin City University (DCU) and Dundalk Institute of Technology and they focus on the use of virtual laboratories as a teaching tool for the chemical sciences.

Figure 4. Prof. Frances Heaney and Prof. Denise Rooney, Maynooth University, speaking about the Virtual Labs Team during the celebration event for the RSC Team Prize for Excellence in Higher Education

Feedback

In order to plan for the next meeting, which will take place in March / April 2028 in Technological University Dublin, feedback was sought from participants, and a selection of the comments follow;

- ‘The combination of longer & short talks worked well. Great choice and variety of speakers’
- ‘Mixture of long and bite sized talks worked well’
- ‘Great to hear experience and ongoing initiatives across the country’

Acknowledgements

The 13th Irish Variety in Chemistry Education meeting was made possible by the financial support of several sponsors; the Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, the Virtual Labs HCl P3 Initiative and the Royal Society of Chemistry, Chemistry Education Research Group. Sponsorship allowed the registration fee to be kept to 20 euro which is an important element in making the meeting inclusive.

We are also very grateful to our speakers and to all participants.

Previous Events in this Series

Reports are available for some previous events in the series: 12th Irish Variety in Chemistry Education meeting, 2024, <https://irishvarietyinchemistryeducation2024.wordpress.com/programme-information/>

9th Irish Variety in Chemistry Education meeting, *Education in Chemistry*, 2014, <https://edu.rsc.org/event-news/conference-report-irish-variety-in-chemistry-education/2010018.article>

8th Irish Variety in Chemistry Education meeting, 2012, <http://michaelseery.com/8th-irish-variety-in-chemistry-teaching-meeting>